

SPACE PROPULSION 2026
BARI, ITALY | 18 – 21 MAY 2026

DESIGN OF A MODULAR 100-N BIPROPELLANT THRUSTER PROTOTYPE BASED ON HYDROGEN PEROXIDE AND HYDROGEN

Fabio Faraoni⁽¹⁾, Alberto Sarritzu⁽²⁾, Lily Blondel-Canepari⁽³⁾, Angelo Pasini⁽⁴⁾

*University of Pisa, Department of Civil and Industrial Engineering, Space Propulsion Laboratory
Via Girolamo Caruso 8, Pisa, Italy, 56122*

⁽¹⁾ Email: fabio.faraoni@phd.unipi.it ⁽²⁾ Email: alberto.sarritzu@ing.unipi.it
⁽³⁾ Email: lily.blondel@ing.unipi.it ⁽⁴⁾ Email: angelo.pasini@unipi.it

KEYWORDS: Green Propellants, Hydrogen Peroxide, Water Propulsion, Bipropellant Thrusters

ABSTRACT:

This paper presents the design of a 100-N bipropellant thruster prototype utilizing high-test peroxide (HTP) and gaseous hydrogen. Developed under the Green SWaP project, this engine serves as a testbed to empirically evaluate the ignition and combustion characteristics of these green propellants. While conventional water electrolysis propulsion relies on gaseous oxygen and hydrogen, the substitution of HTP significantly improves overall propellant storage density and orbital maneuvering capability. To facilitate rapid hardware reconfiguration during testing, the thruster employs a strictly modular architecture comprising a catalytic bed, an interchangeable injector plate, an ignition module, and a passive heat-sink combustion chamber. The design accommodates nominal chamber pressures of 10 and 15 bar and evaluates multiple gas-gas injection geometries. Preliminary sizing, material selection, and diagnostic instrumentation are detailed to support the forthcoming hot-fire experimental campaign.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Green Propellants and Water Propulsion

The development and adoption of space propulsion systems utilizing green propellants have expanded significantly in recent years. These alternative propellants reduce the costs, risks, and delays traditionally associated with toxic options, such as hydrazine and nitrogen tetroxide. Recent technological advancements have facilitated the market entry of novel propulsion concepts, notably water-based space propulsion. This approach is currently experiencing renewed interest across various research organizations and industry sectors.

Water serves as an exceptionally economical, stable, non-corrosive, and safe fluid. Utilizing water as a propellant also presents unique synergies for specific mission profiles. Because water exists as ice on numerous celestial bodies throughout the solar system, it presents a viable option for spacecraft refuel-

ing via In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU). Manned missions stand to benefit particularly from water-based propulsion, as onboard Environmental Control and Life Support Systems (ECLSS) are inherently designed for water management. Furthermore, the hazard posed to a crew by a leak of water or its derivatives is substantially lower than that of a hydrazine leak. These distinct advantages warrant serious consideration in the evaluation of future propulsion systems.

Water-based space propulsion can be achieved through various methods. The technologies currently receiving the most attention, and consequently possessing the highest Technology Readiness Levels (TRL), are resistojets, Water Electrolysis Propulsion (WEP), Hall effect thrusters, and microwave electrothermal thrusters. Among these, WEP provides the highest thrust levels, making it ideally suited for large spacecraft such as Orbital Transfer Vehicles (OTVs) and space stations.

WEP systems utilize water electrolysis to generate gaseous hydrogen and oxygen in stoichiometric proportions. These gases are subsequently burned in a bipropellant chemical thruster to produce thrust. Because the gaseous propellants are cold and non-hypergolic, ignition is typically catalytic. WEP effectively operates at the intersection of electrical and chemical propulsion. While propellant production requires time and continuous electrical power, once the gases are generated, rapid maneuvers can be executed without further straining the spacecraft's power budget.

The primary system-level challenges for WEP today include volume constraints, waste heat management, and the long-term reliability and cost of the propellant conversion system, which must operate for many years during the mission [1].

Conventional WEP also presents limitations inherent to the selected propellants. Water electrolysis yields gaseous oxygen and hydrogen (GO_2/GH_2) in a stoichiometric ratio, which burn at extreme temperatures reaching up to 3400 K. Such high combustion temperatures result in lower practical combustion efficiencies, as a significant percentage of the hydrogen (up to 60/70% by mass) must be di-

verted for film cooling to protect the combustion chamber walls [2]. Without this cooling, the chamber would require construction from expensive refractory materials. Another disadvantage of conventional WEP is the low storage density of the gaseous propellants, even when held at high pressures.

Finally, any GO_2/GH_2 thruster requires an ignition system. WEP typically relies on catalytic ignition, utilizing Platinum Group Metals (PGM) such as platinum, iridium, and bimetallic alloys to promote heterogeneous surface combustion [3, 4]. Ensuring the structural and chemical stability of this catalyst near such extreme combustion temperatures is critical for mission success.

Consequently, modern WEP systems are generally designed for low thrust levels, on the order of 1 N. Only legacy NASA contracts from the late 1980s, awarded to contractors such as Aerojet, Bell Aerospace, and Rocketdyne, have thoroughly investigated medium-to-high thrust in-space propulsion systems intended for early Space Station concepts [5].

1.2. The Green SWaP Project

The EU EIC Pathfinder Green SWaP project was established to address the aforementioned limitations of GO_2/GH_2 systems. The primary objective is to develop a WEP architecture utilizing High-Test Peroxide (HTP) and GH_2 , specifically scaled to produce thrust on the order of hundreds of Newtons. By converting water directly into HTP and GH_2 , the system yields a liquid oxidizer that is significantly denser than its gaseous counterpart (up to 40% denser than liquid water) and over 10 times denser than GO_2 pressurized at 100 bar.

To advance the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of this propulsion concept, a consortium of European partners is developing several critical subsystems [6]. This integrated effort encompasses a water conversion system investigating electrocatalytic, photocatalytic, and plasma-based synthesis methods; an H_2O_2 concentration unit; an inflatable GH_2 storage module; and the propulsion hardware itself, which includes a 200-N HTP/ GH_2 primary thruster and a 1-N GH_2 solar-thermal thruster. The University of Pisa serves as the project coordinator and directs the technical development of the primary bipropellant engine.

1.3. Scope of the Work

This paper focuses on the design of the first modular, subscale prototype of the bipropellant thruster fueled by HTP and GH_2 . Section 2 presents the ideal performance of the engine and explains the criteria used to select the operating design point for this first prototype. Section 3 addresses the design philosophy and necessary trade-offs, reviewing the

various engine subsystems and the technical solutions implemented. Section 4 explores the current state of gas-gas injection. It details the technical reasoning and initial sizing behind promising injector geometries. Finally, Section 5 describes the diagnostic instrumentation chosen for the engine. It explains which properties are valuable to measure and how these sensors physically interface with the thruster.

2. THEORETICAL PERFORMANCE AND THRUSTER REQUIREMENTS

2.1. Propellant Thermochemistry and Ideal Performance

The combination of High-Test Peroxide (HTP) and gaseous hydrogen presents unique thermodynamic characteristics, primarily because the propellants are not intrinsically hypergolic. Cold liquid HTP and GH_2 will not combust spontaneously upon contact. To achieve reliable ignition, this thruster leverages a technique common to HTP-based systems: the catalytic decomposition of the liquid oxidizer is utilized to drive the thermal auto-ignition of the fuel. As the HTP decomposes, it rapidly transitions into gaseous oxygen and water vapor, releasing a substantial amount of thermal energy. This highly exothermic reaction vaporizes the oxidizer stream, elevating its temperature to roughly 1220 K for a 98% HTP concentration.

Total engine performance is conventionally evaluated by decoupling thrust into two fundamental parameters. The first is the characteristic velocity, c^* , which serves as a direct measure of propellant thermochemical quality and combustion chamber efficiency, independent of nozzle geometry. The second is the thrust coefficient, C_F , which quantifies the nozzle expansion efficiency. Their product yields the specific impulse, I_{sp} , representing the overall efficiency with which the engine converts propellant mass into thrust. The fundamental relationship between these quantities is given by Equation 1.

$$T = \dot{m} C_F c^* = \dot{m} I_{sp} g_0 \quad (1)$$

In vehicle architectures where volumetric constraints supersede mass limitations, as is the case when storing gaseous propellants onboard spacecraft, the volume specific impulse, I_v , emerges as a paramount figure of merit. This metric evaluates the propulsive efficiency per unit of storage volume and is defined by Equation 2.

$$I_v = I_{sp} \rho_{\text{bulk}} = I_{sp} \frac{ROF + 1}{\frac{ROF}{\rho_{\text{ox}}} + \frac{1}{\rho_{\text{fu}}}} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_{bulk} represents the average density of the total propellant load, which depends on the oxidizer-

to-fuel ratio (ROF). Additionally, the choice of propellants dictates the combustion temperature (T_c) that the chamber walls must withstand.

Because this engine is designed for integration into a broader water-based propulsion system, it must operate in stoichiometric conditions. The value of the stoichiometric ROF is strictly a function of the selected HTP mass concentration (c_{HTP}), defined by Equation 3.

$$ROF_{sto} = \frac{M_{H_2O_2}}{M_{H_2} \cdot c_{HTP}} \quad (3)$$

where $M_{H_2O_2}$ and M_{H_2} denote the molar masses of hydrogen peroxide and molecular hydrogen, respectively, and c_{HTP} represents the mass fraction of the hydrogen peroxide solution. Consequently, ROF_{sto} increases from 17.2 to 19.9 as the HTP concentration decreases from 98% to 85%.

These interdependent theoretical parameters are plotted as a function of the oxidizer-to-fuel ratio in Figure 1 and Figure 2. A comprehensive comparison of HTP/GH₂ against other propellants is provided in Faraoni et al. [7].

At the stoichiometric mixture ratio of 17.22 for 98% HTP/GH₂, the characteristic velocity (c^*) is 1854 m/s, roughly 6% higher than peak hydrazine bipropellant performance. The vacuum specific impulse (I_{sp}) is 374.1 s and the equilibrium combustion temperature (T_c) reaches approximately 2900 K. This combustion temperature is roughly 10% lower than that of conventional toxic bipropellants and 17% lower than stoichiometric GO₂/GH₂ systems.

2.2. System-Level Performance and Volumetric Constraints

Although a high volume specific impulse (I_v) suggests a theoretical advantage for the HTP/GH₂ architecture, thermochemical performance alone does not guarantee a corresponding increase in orbital maneuvering capability (Δv). Vehicle performance must account for the structural mass required for propellant storage. High-pressure gaseous propellants require heavy Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessels (COPVs). This structural penalty increases the vehicle dry mass, thereby reducing the achievable Δv regardless of the mass specific impulse (I_{sp}).

To evaluate this effect, a systems-level study was conducted under a volumetric constraint of $V_{tank} = 1.35 \text{ m}^3$, reflecting the baseline requirements of the Green SWaP Kick Stage [8]. To accurately model propellant mass, the real-gas densities for GO₂ and GH₂ were calculated at 300 bar using the Redlich-Kwong Equation of State. The total allowable propellant mass for each architecture was then derived using the mixture's bulk density.

Figure 1. Ideal performance characteristics (I_{sp} , c^* , T_c) as a function of oxidizer-to-fuel ratio. The stoichiometric operating point for the water-based architectures is indicated by square symbols.

Figure 2. Volumetric specific impulse comparison between the two water-based propulsion systems.

Both the reference GO_2/GH_2 system and the proposed HTP/GH_2 system were constrained to existing commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) tank technologies from manufacturers such as MT Aerospace and ArianeGroup. The structural tankage fractions ($\beta = m_{\text{tank}}/m_{\text{fluid}}$) were derived using representative flight-proven hardware as proxies: 0.50 for 310-bar GO_2 and 10.0 for 310-bar GH_2 (based on He/N_2 COPVs), and 0.05 for 20-bar liquid HTP (based on titanium PMD tanks) [9, 10]. The velocity increment was then computed using the Tsiolkovsky rocket equation:

$$\Delta v = I_{sp} g_0 \ln \left(1 + \frac{m_{\text{prop}}}{m_{\text{dry}}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where m_{prop} is the total propellant mass dictated by the allowable tank volume, and m_{dry} is the total dry mass of the vehicle. The dry mass is defined as $m_{\text{dry}} = m_{\text{pay}} + m_{\text{engine}} + \beta_{\text{ox}} m_{\text{ox}} + \beta_{\text{f}} m_{\text{f}}$, where m_{pay} is the useful payload mass, m_{engine} is the fixed mass of the thruster and supporting avionics (assumed as 15 kg), and β_{ox} and β_{f} are the structural fractions for the oxidizer (m_{ox}) and fuel (m_{f}) tanks, respectively.

Figure 3 illustrates the available Δv across a range of payload masses. The analysis demonstrates that the HTP/GH_2 architecture provides a higher orbital maneuvering capability compared to conventional WEP for a given tank volume, despite the lower I_{sp} . This is the result of the combined effects of a denser oxidizer and a lighter oxidizer tank. It must be noted, however, that GH_2 COPVs still impose a significant parasitic mass on both systems. Future integration of inflatable hydrogen tanks, currently under development within the Green SWaP framework, aims to further alleviate this structural limitation.

Figure 3. Orbital maneuvering capability (Δv) as a function of useful payload mass for a fixed tank volume of 1.35 m^3 operating at a 300-bar storage pressure.

2.3. Subscale Design Point

Theoretical performance estimates and the operational requirements of a water-based propulsion system dictated the operating point for both the engine and its initial prototype [11]. The prototype unit is primarily designed to investigate the ignition characteristics of gaseous hydrogen with the decomposition products of High-Test Peroxide (HTP).

Nominal combustion chamber pressure was established a priori based on typical values of similar bipropellant systems. While a higher chamber pressure facilitates reliable ignition and enhances overall performance, it imposes stricter demands on the upstream fluidic systems and reduces residual autonomy. Consequently, the prototype is configured to operate at two distinct combustion chamber pressures: 10 bar and 15 bar. The principal specifications of this initial prototype are detailed in Table 1.

The nominal engine parameters were calculated using the NASA Chemical Equilibrium with Applications (CEA) program, incorporating boundary layer and divergence loss corrections. The resulting fixed inputs and derived characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Engine sizing was constrained to a 100-N vacuum thrust target at a stoichiometric mixture ratio. The decision to develop a 100-N subscale test article, rather than the 200-N project baseline, represents a compromise between thermodynamic scaling limitations and test facility logistics.

Scaling down the thrust level imposes three primary engineering penalties. First, a higher surface-to-volume ratio increases fractional heat loss to the chamber walls. Second, a reduced chamber length

Table 1. Specifications of the thruster prototype.

Parameter	10 bar	15 bar
<i>Fixed Design Constraints</i>		
Propellants	98% HTP / GH ₂	
Vacuum Thrust Target	100 N	
Mixture Ratio (O/F)	17.22 (Stoich.)	
Propellant Temperature	298.15 K	
Conical Half-Angle	15°	
<i>Calculated Engine Parameters</i>		
Total Mass Flow	27.22 g/s	27.10 g/s
Oxidizer Mass Flow	25.73 g/s	25.61 g/s
Fuel Mass Flow	1.49 g/s	1.49 g/s
Vacuum I_{sp}	374.6 s	376.2 s
Throat Diameter (D_t)	8.05 mm	6.56 mm
Matched Area Ratio (ϵ)	2.25	2.95
Expected S.L. Thrust*	61.64 N	65.77 N

*Includes boundary layer displacement and conical divergence thrust corrections.

decreases bulk residence time, risking the expulsion of unreacted propellants. Finally, the lower mass flow rate dictates smaller injector orifices. To maintain standard machining tolerances, the total number of injection elements must be reduced, which inherently compromises propellant mixing and combustion efficiency.

Despite these performance penalties, the subscale approach was adopted for its critical operational advantages. Halving the thrust proportionally reduces propellant consumption, thereby doubling the achievable firing duration per test. This maximizes data collection and minimizes the procedural downtime associated with facility tank refilling. Ultimately, these logistical benefits conclusively outweigh the subscale engineering constraints.

3. MODULAR PROTOTYPE ARCHITECTURE

The initial subscale prototype was developed to empirically evaluate the ignition transients and short-duration combustion characteristics of the HTP/GH₂ propellants combination. Specifically, testing must verify the autogenous ignition limits of gaseous hydrogen when injected into hot HTP decomposition products, alongside determining combustion stability boundaries and the required characteristic chamber length.

3.1. Design Philosophy

Because the autoignition and combustion performance are highly sensitive to variables such as injector geometry and nominal chamber pressure, the engineering model was designed with a strictly modular architecture. To facilitate rapid hardware reconfiguration and iterative parameter isolation between hot-fire tests, the thruster assembly is segmented

into four distinct, interchangeable modules. These modules are listed below and illustrated schematically in Figure 4.

- **Catalytic Bed:** Decomposes the liquid HTP to provide a high-temperature, oxidizer-rich gaseous stream (O₂ and H₂O vapor) to the main chamber.
- **Injection:** Hosts removable plates that inject the two gaseous propellants into the combustion chamber.
- **Ignition Ring:** Accommodates a direct-spark or supplementary ignition source, acting as a redundant system in case autoignition proves insufficient or delayed.
- **Combustion Chamber:** Contains the chemical reaction and accelerates the exhaust gases generating thrust.

Figure 4. Engine modular architecture schematic.

3.2. Catalytic Bed

The main purpose of the catalytic bed is to completely decompose the HTP flow prior to chamber injection. This decomposition reaction is greatly accelerated by the presence of some catalyst materials. Because this reaction must occur rapidly within a confined volume, catalytic structures must have a high surface area and be capable of withstanding severe thermomechanical stress, active-site poisoning, and high-temperature sintering.

To satisfy these criteria, the active catalyst is typically deposited onto a porous, thermally stable ceramic substrate, such as aluminum oxide (alumina, Al₂O₃), in either monolithic or pelletized form. Platinum remains the most effective element for the heterogeneous decomposition of HTP, followed closely by other Platinum Group Metals (PGMs) and manganese oxides [12]. Consequently, initial baseline testing for this prototype will employ platinum deposited on alpha-alumina (α -Al₂O₃) pellets with diameters of 0.4 mm and 0.6 mm, such as those illustrated in Figure 5.

Inside the catalytic bed, the pellets are tightly packed by two thin metal meshes and a compression spring. This retention system compensates for thermal expansion and particle settling, ensuring the bed remains strictly compacted during firing tests.

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of Pt/ α -Al₂O₃ pellets with diameter of 0.6 mm (left) and 0.4 (right) [13].

Subsequent phases of the Green SWaP project will evaluate alternative, non-Critical Raw Material (CRM) catalysts. Because these substitutes are anticipated to yield lower baseline reactivity than platinum, the hardware incorporates modular inserts to extend the active bed length as required. In order to monitor the HTP decomposition profile, multiple diagnostic ports are distributed along the longitudinal axis. The fully instrumented assembly, configured with a nozzle for atmospheric monopropellant testing, is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Catalytic bed fully integrated for monopropellant firing tests, including pressure transducers (green) and thermocouples (blue).

The thermodynamic and kinetic performance of the catalytic bed is governed primarily by its internal operating pressure and the mass flux, or bed load, defined as $G = \dot{m}/A$. A nominal operating pressure of 18 bar was selected to promote rapid and complete HTP decomposition. Furthermore, to minimize engine startup transients, a relatively high specific mass flux of 50 kg/(s·m²) was selected. This accelerates the startup capability, at the expense of increased catalyst wear and the need for a longer bed to ensure complete fluid decomposition [14].

Mechanically, the catalyst module is anchored by a structural flange. This flange serves a dual purpose: it provides the sealed connection for the injection module and acts as the physical interface of the engine to the thrust balance. The catalytic bed walls have various diagnostic ports for temperature and pressure measurements (more details in Section 5). The pressure sensors are recessed with respect to the internal wall to protect them from the hot and oxidizing environment. These recessed interfaces are

achieved by welding 1/8-inch stainless steel tubes on the sides. Finally, leak-free liquid HTP injection is guaranteed by a welded modified compression fitting, sized to accommodate the 1/4-inch feed line.

3.3. Injection

Following the decomposition of HTP, the oxidizer must be injected and efficiently mixed with gaseous hydrogen within the combustion chamber. Because optimal injection geometry is dependent on the specific propellant combination, and existing literature regarding HTP/GH₂ combustion remains limited (as detailed in Section 4), the injection module requires a flexible design to facilitate rapid iteration and testing.

To satisfy this requirement, the injection module features interchangeable injector plates. These plates can be manufactured in 310S stainless steel or Inconel 718, either through conventional machining or additive manufacturing techniques. Structurally, each plate is secured by four M3 socket head cap screws. To ensure an absolute seal between the fuel and oxidizer streams prior to injection, the internal interface utilizes a 37-degree flared conical seal, designed in accordance with the SAE J514 standard [15].

The injection module hosts pressure measurements at two distinct locations. The first measurement, taken upstream of the oxidizer injection, monitors the outlet of the catalytic bed and the injector pressure drop. The second one records the combustion chamber pressure, which is the primary metric for overall engine performance. This is done by means of an orifice adjacent to the injector plate.

The 3D model of this design is illustrated in Figure 7, equipped with a baseline 4-on-1 impinging injector plate and with the two pressure transducers.

Figure 7. Injection module with GH₂ inlet tube (on the left) and pressure transducers (on the right).

3.4. Combustion Chamber and Ignition

The final components of the prototype are the ignition module and the combustion chamber. Together, they form the volume where gaseous hydrogen reacts with the oxygen-rich decomposition products of HTP. Because the thruster is designed to operate at a stoichiometric mixture ratio, complete combustion

produces an exhaust stream composed entirely of high-temperature steam.

To survive this thermal environment without active cooling, both modules rely on a passive heat-sink design. This cooling technique requires adequately thick walls and materials with high thermal conductivity. Consequently, the material selection process focused on two primary candidates: AISI 310S stainless steel and a precipitation-hardened CuCrZr copper alloy. Figure 8 shows the transient thermal response of these materials evaluated using a model detailed in previous work [7].

Figure 8. Transient evolution of inner wall temperature at the throat for a 5.0 mm wall thickness. Circles indicate the operational limit for each respective material.

AISI 310S provides high maximum operational temperatures, approximately 20% higher than standard AISI 316 stainless steel, and better thermal conductivity than superalloys like Inconel 718. Crucially, it maintains chemical compatibility and structural integrity in highly oxidizing environments. Conversely, the CuCrZr alloy offers a thermal conductivity over 20 times greater than that of 310S, making thicker walls highly effective for heat dissipation.

However, this copper alloy has a substantially lower maximum service temperature and inferior oxidation resistance compared to stainless steel. Furthermore, it features lower machinability and higher procurement costs. For these reasons, AISI 310S was selected as the baseline material.

To ensure adequate flow residence time, the combustion chamber features an internal diameter of 25 mm and a characteristic length (L^*) of 1.2 m. Two chamber configurations were designed, targeting nominal operating pressures of 10 bar and 15 bar. While the 15-bar variant imposes a higher thermal flux on the walls, it inherently improves overall engine performance and increases the probability of autoignition. As illustrated in Figure 10, both chamber designs have a uniform wall thickness of 5 mm and a 15-degree half-angle conical nozzle, which is matched to the external atmospheric pressure.

Figure 9. Transient evolution of inner wall temperature at the throat for an increased wall thickness of 8.0 mm. CuCrZr is the material benefiting the most from the added thermal mass.

Figure 10. Combustion chamber geometries designed for 10-bar and 15-bar nominal operating pressures, featuring a uniform 5 mm wall thickness.

Finally, the ignition module provides a redundant starting mechanism should autoignition fail. This component functions as an extension of the chamber's cylindrical section, designed to house a standard 14 mm threaded spark plug or other ignition devices. When direct ignition is omitted, the port is sealed with a solid blanking plug to maintain the structural integrity of the chamber. Figure 11 illustrates the 3D assembly of these two modules.

Figure 11. Combustion chamber and ignition modules assembly with blanking plug.

3.5. Sealing Interfaces

The mechanical interfaces between the thruster modules require reliable static seals to prevent the escape of high-pressure internal gases. Gaskets accomplish this by plastically deforming under mechanical load to fill microscopic surface asperities.

Standard aerospace sealing materials, including graphite (in sheet or braided forms), mica, and metal contacts, were evaluated based on chemical compatibility, maximum operating temperatures, requisite clamping forces, and surface finish tolerances.

For this initial prototype, standard solid copper gaskets (DIN 7603 Form A) with internal diameter of 42 mm, external diameter of 49 mm, and thickness of 2 mm were selected. To optimize the seal and accommodate potential thermal softening of the copper, the flanges employ a modified tongue-and-groove architecture. One mating face provides a flat seating surface, while the opposing face incorporates a continuous, localized stress-concentrating spike. This configuration, illustrated in Figure 12, forces the spike to physically embed into the ductile copper, creating a pressure seal and retaining the gasket at elevated temperatures.

Figure 12. Detailed view of the sealing interface.

Because copper is susceptible to high-temperature oxidation and strength degradation, these gaskets are not suited for continuous, steady-state thermal operation. However, for the short-duration transient firings planned for this prototype, these thermal limitations are acceptable. Copper was prioritized primarily for its commercial availability and its ability to reduce the requisite mechanical preload. The combination of a soft, ductile material and a stress-concentrating spike significantly lowers the necessary clamping force. Consequently, this minimizes thread wear and fatigue on the six M4 socket head cap screws over repeated assembly cycles. The complete integration of these sequentially sealed modular components, culminating in the 100-N subscale prototype, is presented in Figure 13.

4. INJECTOR DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING TRADE-OFFS

The geometry of the propellant injection system has great influence on combustion efficiency, heat transfer, and engine stability. This geometry can take various shapes, such as impinging jet, shear-coaxial, showerhead, and pintle configurations. Furthermore, these designs can be implemented as a single, centralized element or distributed across a multi-element faceplate to enhance mixing.

4.1. Gas-Gas Injection Dynamics

In the vast majority of contemporary space propulsion systems, at least one propellant is injected in the liquid phase. This holds true for large-scale conventional liquid rocket engines, as well as those utilizing modern green storable propellants. Consequently, the injector must primarily govern the atomization and subsequent vaporization of the liquid phase before chemical reaction can occur.

Pure gas-gas injection dynamics are less documented in the literature. As mentioned before, foundational research on small-to-medium scale engines (ranging from 400 N to 1 kN) was conducted in parallel by Aerojet, Rocketdyne, and Bell Aerospace during the 1980s.

In modern contexts, gas-gas injection studies predominantly focus on main combustion chamber injectors for large-scale engines operating on the Full-Flow Staged Combustion (FFSC) cycle. Such cycles route the entire propellant mass flow through pre-burners to drive the turbomachinery, ensuring both fuel and oxidizer enter the main chamber completely gasified. For these applications, the shear-coaxial and swirl-coaxial configurations remain the most thoroughly investigated. Recent numerical and experimental studies of GO_2/GH_2 systems have parameterized various geometric factors [16–18]. The prevailing consensus indicates that a shear-coaxial geometry, specifically featuring a central oxidizer core surrounded by an annular fuel stream, yields the highest combustion efficiency and maintains superior stability during off-design operating conditions.

The thruster architecture at hand, however, differs from pure GO_2/GH_2 systems. The oxidizer stream derived from HTP decomposition arrives at the injector significantly hotter, yet it possesses a lower mass fraction of available oxygen due to the high concentration of superheated steam. While literature design criteria are not directly applicable to this exact case, the fundamental momentum-exchange principles of gas-gas shear mixing continue to serve as the baseline heuristic for the proposed injector design.

4.2. Challenges of High ROF at Subscale

Applying these design criteria to the 100-N HTP/ GH_2 prototype introduces severe manufacturing limitations. As the engine must operate at a stoichiometric Oxidizer-to-Fuel Ratio (ROF) of 17.2, the mass flow rates are heavily skewed. At nominal 100-N thrust, the oxidizer mass flow is approximately 25.6 g/s, compared to 1.5 g/s for the fuel.

Scaling a conventional single-element shear-coaxial injector to these parameters reveals a fundamental geometric constraint. To maintain an adequate fuel injection pressure drop with such a low mass flow

Figure 13. Full 3D assembly of the modular 100-N HTP/GH₂ thruster prototype, illustrating the integration of the various components and the thrust-balance cradle connection.

Figure 14. Schematic of the conventional shear-coaxial injector geometry.

rate, the outer GH₂ annulus must be reduced to a radial gap of approximately 100 to 200 μm , as illustrated in Figure 14. Tolerances of this magnitude fall below the reliable thresholds of conventional machining and standard Selective Laser Melting (SLM) additive manufacturing techniques.

To resolve the manufacturing constraints of the standard shear-coaxial geometry while preserving the mixing benefits of shear layer instability, the injection configuration can be inverted. In this inverted shear-coaxial configuration, the gaseous hydrogen flows through the central core, while the HTP flows through the outer annulus. Consequently, the dimensions of the various elements become significantly easier to manufacture.

A preliminary sizing under the same nominal 10-bar baseline constraints ($\Delta P_{ox} = 15\%$, $\Delta P_f = 20\%$) was performed, resulting in a central GH₂ hole of 2.12 mm, bounded by a 0.30 mm separation wall and a 2.69 mm thick oxidizer annulus. **Case A** in Figure 15 illustrates this configuration.

A drawback of this geometry is the reduced contact area between the fuel and oxidizer flows, which is one of the main drivers of combustion efficiency. To increase the mixing perimeter, a central post could be placed into the center of the fuel core (**Case B**). By forcing the hydrogen outward into an annulus, the mixing perimeter increases to 13.6 mm. This represents a nearly 60% increase in direct shear

contact area compared to the simple hole configuration. Additionally, the central post could be recessed to further enhance mixing.

Figure 15. Schematic of the inverted shear-coaxial injection geometry.

A simpler alternative selected for the initial test campaign is a 4-on-1 impinging injector plate in which the central hydrogen orifice is surrounded by four converging oxidizer jets. By angling these oxidizer holes inward at 30 degrees, the streams are forced to intersect the central fuel jet at a fixed impingement point downstream of the injector face, generating intense turbulent mixing. Figure 16 illustrates the results of a preliminary sizing of this configuration.

Beyond machining tolerances, a significant challenge in the injector design for this prototype is managing the high injection velocities. While the fully gaseous state of the propellants eliminates the need for chamber length dedicated to atomization and evaporation, the small scale of the engine demands careful consideration of injection velocities. These are primarily governed by the nominal pressure drops (ΔP) across the injection manifolds.

Table 2. Sizing of the selected injection architectures evaluated at a chamber pressure of 10 bar. Injection velocities (v) and local Mach numbers (M) are derived using 1D isentropic compressible flow relations.

Configuration	ΔP_{ox} [%]	ΔP_f [%]	v_{ox} [m/s]	v_f [m/s]	M_{ox}	M_f	Figure of merit
Impinging 4-on-1	15	15	352.5	580.4	0.48	0.45	$J \approx 1.01$
Shear-Coaxial (Case A)	10	20	291.8	660.9	0.39	0.52	$V_r = 2.27$
Shear-Coaxial Post (Case B)	10	20	291.8	660.9	0.39	0.52	$V_r = 2.27$

Figure 16. Schematic of the 4-on-1 impinging injector geometry. Front view on the top, section view on the bottom.

Crucially, these pressure drops also serve to decouple combustion chamber acoustic instabilities from the feed lines. Table 2 details the selected pressure drops and the resulting injection velocities for this preliminary sizing.

For the impinging architecture, a uniform 15% pressure drop is employed. This stiffens the feed system while maintaining an optimal momentum balance between the impinging streams ($J \approx 1.01$). Multiple versions of these impinging injector plates will be manufactured to investigate the effect of injection velocity.

Conversely, the shear-coaxial architectures are penalized by a low velocity ratio (V_r). To partially mitigate this, the manifold pressure drops were decoupled, raising the velocity ratio to 2.27. Nevertheless, the absolute injection velocities remain on the high side; experimental hot-fire testing will be required to establish actual combustion efficiencies and refine these preliminary designs.

Prior to experimental testing, the discharge coefficient (C_d) of each injector configuration will be characterized. Calibration will be performed *in situ* on the assembled system using nitrogen (GN_2) as an inert surrogate gas. By measuring the pressure drop across the injector at varying steady-state GN_2 mass flow rates, the effective area of the orifices can be determined empirically.

5. ENGINE DIAGNOSTICS FOR PERFORMANCE CHARACTERIZATION

The primary objective of the experimental campaign is to obtain a first evaluation of the thruster performance and combustion stability. The key efficiency metrics for the bipropellant thruster are the specific impulse (I_{sp}), characteristic velocity (c^*), and thrust coefficient (C_f).

$$I_{sp} = \frac{F}{\dot{m}g_0}, \quad c^* = \frac{p_c A_t}{\dot{m}}, \quad C_f = \frac{F}{p_c A_t} \quad (5)$$

where A_t is the nozzle throat area, F is the thrust force, p_c is the chamber pressure and \dot{m} is the total mass flow rate.

Additionally, the characterization of the thruster in its monopropellant configuration requires the measurement of the temperature and pressure downstream of the catalytic bed for the evaluation of the temperature efficiency $\eta_{\Delta T}$ and the characteristic velocity efficiency η_{c^*} .

$$\eta_{\Delta T} = \frac{T_{dec} - T_{amb}}{T_{ad} - T_{amb}} \quad (6)$$

$$\eta_{c^*} = \frac{p_{dec} A_{t,bed} / \dot{m}_{ox}}{\sqrt{R T_{ad} / \gamma} [(\gamma + 1) / 2]^{(\gamma + 1) / 2(\gamma - 1)}} \quad (7)$$

The sensors needed to measure the required quantities are: load cells, pressure transducers, mass flow meters and thermocouples. A list of these sensors and their respective locations is reported in Table 3.

Temperature is measured using 1-mm Inconel-sheathed Type-K thermocouples. There is no direct measurement of combustion chamber gas temperatures as they exceed the survivability limits of these probes. Static pressures are measured with miniature high-temperature pressure transducers. To protect the membranes from direct hot gas temperatures, the transducers are recessed using 1/8-inch tubes. The axial thrust is measured by a 200-N load cell aligned with the thrust vector.

Finally, the HTP mass flow rate is measured by a Coriolis mass flow meter, while the low-density GH_2 flow is measured by a thermal mass flow meter.

Table 3. Summary of thruster instrumentation, sensor locations, and diagnostic purposes.

Sensor Type	Location	Diagnostic Purpose
<i>Temperature Measurements</i>		
Thermocouple (Type-K)	Bed Inlet	HTP inlet temperature and thermal soak-back
	Bed Middle	HTP thermal decomposition profile
	Bed Outlet	Verification of full oxidizer decomposition
<i>Pressure Measurements</i>		
Piezoresistive Pressure Transducer	Bed Inlet	HTP supply pressure
	Bed Outlet	Catalytic bed pressure drop
	Pre-injection	Manifold ΔP and dynamic response
	Thrust Chamber	For performance and stability analysis
<i>Flow and Thrust Measurements</i>		
Flow Meter (Coriolis)	Test Bench	HTP mass flow rate for c^* and I_{sp}
Flow Meter (Thermal)	Test Bench	GH ₂ mass flow rate for c^* and I_{sp}
Load Cell	Thrust Balance	Thrust measurement

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work progressed from the initial performance requirements to the detailed design of the thruster. The necessity for iterative experimental testing to characterize ignition and combustion dictated a highly modular design, comprising four distinct sections in series. The first module is a spring-loaded catalytic bed with variable length and injection geometry. This configuration ensures complete HTP decomposition and facilitates future evaluations of alternative catalysts. The second module utilizes an interchangeable injector plate, allowing the evaluation of various gas-gas injection geometries. A third module accommodates a direct ignition system to provide redundancy should autogenous ignition prove unreliable. Finally, the fourth module consists of a passive heat-sink cooled combustion chamber.

The specific engineering challenges associated with injector design for this unconventional propellant combination were addressed. Consequently, an impinging configuration and a shear-coaxial geometry were identified as the baselines for empirical characterization.

Finally, the key performance parameters of the engine guided the selection of the necessary instrumentation to measure temperature, pressure, thrust, and mass flow rates.

This effort concludes the design phase for the first HTP/GH₂ thruster prototype within the Green SWaP project. The program now advances to the manufacturing of the engine components and procurement of the thrust balance and the fluidic test bench. Together, these systems will form the core of the forthcoming test campaigns, which will enable experimental investigation into the ignition dynamics, combustion stability, and overall performance of this novel engine.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project leading to this paper has received funding from the European Union under the European Innovation Council grant agreement N. 101161583. Green SWaP, Green Solar-to-propellant Water Propulsion.

The authors also gratefully acknowledge the Space Propulsion Laboratory at the University of Pisa for providing an inspiring research environment and valuable discussions that supported this study.

8. References

- [1] Sam Wilson, Joseph Hunt, Howard Gray, David Gibbon, and Leonard Bauer. Overview of water propulsion developments at airbus defence & space. In *Space Propulsion Conference*, Glasgow, UK, 2024.
- [2] G. P. Richter and H. G. Price. Proven, long-life hydrogen/oxygen thrust chambers for space station propulsion. In *1986 JANNAF Propulsion Meeting*, New Orleans, LA, 1986. NTRS Report/Patent Number: NAS 1.15:88822.
- [3] Charles Muir and Aaron Knoll. Catalytic combustion of hydrogen and oxygen for an electrolysis micro-propulsion system. *Journal of the British Interplanetary Society*, 72:2–6, 2019.

- [4] Minsig Hwang, Tae-Seong Rho, and Hyoung Jin Lee. Conceptual design and performance analysis of water electrolysis propulsion system with catalytic igniter for CubeSats. *Acta Astronautica*, 200:316–328, 2022.
- [5] Brian D. Reed and Steven J. Schneider. Hydrogen/oxygen auxiliary propulsion technology. In *Conference on Advanced Space Exploration Initiative Technologies*, Cleveland, OH, September 1991. AIAA, NASA, and OAI.
- [6] Angelo Pasini, Alberto Sarritzu, Lily Blondel-Canepari, Fabio Faraoni, Francesco Pineider, Luca Labella, Simona Samaritani, Alessio Gabbani, Alberto Naldoni, Arianna Giacchero, Gabriele Centi, Rosalba Passalacqua, Stefano Vannuzzi, Manfred Kraut, Alexander Navarrete Muñoz, Sk Amir Ali, Candice Masucci-Templier, Leonardo Dall’Osto, Riccardo Cambertoni, and Angelo Cervone. Converting water into performant propellants for in-space propulsion: Overview of the green SWaP project. In *76th International Astronautical Congress (IAC)*, Sydney, Australia, 2025. IAC-25-D2,8,11,x100386.
- [7] Fabio Faraoni, Alberto Sarritzu, and Angelo Pasini. Performance assessment of an H₂O₂/H₂ bipropellant thruster for innovative water-based space propulsion. In *EUCASS 2025*, Rome, Italy, 2025.
- [8] Riccardo Cambertoni, Leonardo Dall’Osto, Lily Blondel-Canepari, Alberto Sarritzu, Fabio Faraoni, Angelo Pasini, and Angelo Cervone. In-orbit reusable kick-stage enabled by a sustainable space mobility solution harvesting solar energy for onboard fuel production. In *76th International Astronautical Congress (IAC)*, Sydney, Australia, October 2025.
- [9] ArianeGroup. Propellant tanks for monopropellant and bipropellant systems. Catalog, Ariane-Group Orbital Propulsion, Lampoldshausen, Germany, 2021.
- [10] MT Aerospace. Spacecraft propellant tanks. Catalog, MT Aerospace, n.d.
- [11] Alberto Sarritzu, Lily Blondel-Canepari, Fabio Faraoni, Riccardo Cambertoni, Leonardo Dall’Osto, Angelo Cervone, and Angelo Pasini. From water & sunlight to thrust: New propulsion technologies within the green swap project. In *76th International Astronautical Congress (IAC)*, Sydney, Australia, October 2025.
- [12] Lucio Torre, Luca Romeo, Angelo Pasini, Angelo Cervone, Luca d’Agostino, and Fausto Calderazzo. Performance of different catalysts supported on alumina spheres for hydrogen peroxide decomposition. In *43rd AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference & Exhibit*. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Cincinnati, OH, July 2007. AIAA 2007-5466.
- [13] S. Dolci, D. Belli Dell’Amico, A. Pasini, L. Torre, G. Pace, and D. Valentini. Platinum catalysts development for 98% hydrogen peroxide decomposition in pulsed monopropellant thrusters. *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, 31(4):1204–1216, 2015.
- [14] Angelo Cervone, Angelo Pasini, Lucio Torre, L. Romeo, L. Masi, and Luca d’Agostino. High mass flux tests on catalytic beds for h₂o₂ monopropellant thruster. In *Space Propulsion 2010*, San Sebastian, Spain, May 2010. ESA-AAAF.
- [15] SAE International. Sae j514-1: Metallic connections for fluid power and general use - part 1: 37 degree flared fittings. Standard J514-1, SAE International, 2022.
- [16] Timothy D. Smith, Mark D. Klem, Kevin J. Breisacher, Shahram Farhangi, and Robert Sutton. Experimental evaluation of a subscale gaseous hydrogen/gaseous oxygen coaxial rocket injector. Technical Report E-13652, NASA Glenn Research Center, 2002.
- [17] Ping Jin, Mao Li, and Guobiao Cai. Experimental study of hydrogen-rich/oxygen-rich gas-gas injectors. *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, 26(5):1164–1172, 2013.
- [18] Jian Dai and HuanLi Yu. Numerical and experimental investigations of geometrical parameters on GH₂/GO₂ injector. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 106:106187, 2020.